

Fluffy Publication Workflow: Preserving Humanities Research Data with the TextGrid Repository

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Abstract

This paper introduces a revised publication workflow for textual research data in the TextGrid Repository. This repository supports the accessibility and reusability of research outputs in the humanities. The new workflow simplifies the publication process by integrating familiar tools such as TEI, XPath, Git and Jupyter Notebooks. This reduces the technical burden for users, while still ensuring metadata quality controls. For these reasons, we refer to the new workflow as *fluffy*, emphasising its ease of use. The workflow also allows for metadata enrichment without altering original data files, improving overall data and metadata quality and aligning with FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable). By showcasing completed research projects, we demonstrate how the workflow enhances the discoverability and citation of published outputs. The paper concludes by outlining future steps for integrating the workflow with additional services, aiming for a more user-friendly experience and higher metadata quality.

Keywords: data publication, TEI, FAIR principles, Jupyter Notebook, long-term preservation

*Fluffy Publikationsprozess: Erhalt
geisteswissenschaftlicher
Forschungsdaten mit dem TextGrid
Repository*

Zusammenfassung

In diesem Beitrag wird ein überarbeiteter Publikationsablauf für textuelle Forschungsdaten im TextGrid Repository vorgestellt. Dieses Repository unterstützt die Zugänglichkeit und Wiederverwendbarkeit von Forschungsergebnissen in den Geisteswissenschaften. Der neue Workflow vereinfacht den Publikationsprozess durch die Integration bekannter Werkzeuge wie TEI, XPath, Git und Jupyter Notebooks. Dadurch wird der technische Aufwand für die Nutzer verringert, während gleichzeitig die Qualitätskontrolle der Metadaten gewährleistet ist. Aus diesen Gründen bezeichnen wir den neuen Workflow als *fluffig* und betonen damit seine Benutzerfreundlichkeit.

Der Arbeitsablauf ermöglicht auch die Anreicherung von Metadaten, ohne dass die ursprünglichen Datendateien verändert werden müssen. Dadurch wird die Qualität der Daten und Metadaten insgesamt verbessert und den FAIR-Prinzipien (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) entsprochen. Anhand von abgeschlossenen Forschungsprojekten wird gezeigt, wie der Arbeitsablauf die Auffindbarkeit und Zitierbarkeit veröffentlichter Ergebnisse verbessert. Abschließend werden künftige Schritte zur Integration des Workflows mit zusätzlichen Diensten skizziert, um die Benutzerfreundlichkeit zu erhöhen und die Qualität der Metadaten zu verbessern.

Schlüsselwörter: Datenveröffentlichung, TEI, FAIR-Prinzipien, Jupyter Notebook, Langzeitarchivierung

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors have used DeepL Write to proofread the manuscript.

Figures

For all Figures in this article:

1 Introduction

This article presents a newly streamlined workflow for publishing textual research data in the TextGrid Repository (TGR), a platform originally developed within the TextGrid project (Neuroth, Rapp, and Söring 2015). While TGR is designed primarily for TEI-encoded XML documents, it also supports the inclusion of related materials such as images, XSLT transformation sheets, and other supplementary files. Since the project's launch in 2006,¹ the repository has continuously evolved in response to the changing needs of the humanities research community, establishing itself as a sustainable and trusted environment for long-term data preservation.

The new publication workflow (Buddenbohm et al. 2024) significantly lowers the technical barrier for researchers wishing to publish their data in TGR.² It combines user-friendly tools within a Jupyter Notebook environment, offering a modular system based on accessible services and reusable software libraries. The approach is designed to align with the FAIR principles – making data more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable – while also ensuring that metadata remains usable over the long term.

After reviewing this overview of the new, or fluffy, workflow, researchers will be able to assess whether publishing their data in TGR meets their needs and estimate the effort required based on their specific use case.

In addition to the publication workflow, this paper also presents the ecosystem surrounding it. There are three key contributors: DARIAH-DE, a structural part of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures; Text+, a consortium of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), which is the funded project behind these activities; and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

We then present the new publication workflow in detail, outlining each step. This section forms the core of the article and aims to encourage researchers to consider TGR as a platform for publishing their data.

To illustrate how the workflow accommodates different data types and scholarly approaches while offering tailored, visually engaging publication formats, we present three completed data publications: the CLiGS Textbox,³ the MiMoText⁴ collection of eighteenth-century French novels (1751–1800) and the Caucasian

1. The first release of TGR was in 2011.

2. Landing page of TGR: <https://textgridrep.org/?lang=en>

3. Project page: <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-4b8bf6c0-e82e-285f-9f69-66bee06b5e2f#README>

4. <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-c594f9cf-08fd-6086-8379-66c84a31c11a#README>

Folklore project.⁵ These examples highlight how the fluffy workflow not only simplifies data import but also provides a visually rich and project-specific presentation layer for polishing the work of researchers. Ideally, the research data publication benefits both future users and original creators, whose contributions remain visible and citable.

2 The research infrastructure ecosystem

TextGrid started in 2006 as a funded project and subsequently served as a core service in DARIAH-DE and CLARIAH-DE until 2020. The TextGrid Repository remains part of DARIAH-DE, the national node of the DARIAH-ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium).⁶ In order to maintain the TGR independently of project-related funding, the provider institutions decided together with many other DARIAH-DE partner institutions to form an association: GKFI e.V. (the Association for Research Infrastructures in the Humanities and Cultural Studies).⁷ The repository is jointly maintained by the Göttingen State and University Library and by the data and IT service centre GWDG (Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen).

Today, TGR is part of the portfolio at Text+, the consortium for text- and speech-based research data within Germany's NFDI.⁸ As the designated national node of the EOSC, the NFDI provides a potential pathway for integrating and making more visible TGR and its publication workflow within emerging EOSC infrastructures and services (Figure 1). The NFDI comprises 26 subject-specific consortia and one cross-cutting initiative, Base4NFDI, which develops basic services for all participating consortia. These entities were selected through a research-driven evaluation process coordinated by the German Research Foundation (DFG). The consortia span all major research domains, including the humanities and social sciences, life sciences, natural sciences and engineering. The NFDI was launched in three funding rounds between 2020 and 2023.

5. <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-e8f00d53-6ae6-9d31-c530-66cec1a28e16#README>

6. TGR is one of the community services in the DARIAH service catalogue: <https://www.dariah.eu/tools-services/tools-and-services/>

7. Also see <https://forschungsinfrastrukturen.de/doku.php/start> and (Rißler-Pipka and Weimer 2023).

8. Background information on <https://www.nfdi.de/textplus/?lang=en> and <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia/?lang=en>

Figure 1: Screenshot of the service portfolio offered through Text+, specifically showing parts of the new publication workflow using the SSH Open Marketplace as a catalogue service.⁹

Apart from the integration of TGR within the DARIAH and NFDI ecosystems (and potentially EOSC), research data ingested via the publication workflow also appears in the CLARIN ecosystem, for instance in the Virtual Language Observatory.¹⁰

We promote the visibility of cooperation and interoperability within such contexts as CLARIN or the NFDI. For example the SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP, Figure 1) is used to disseminate information on TGR and the new publication workflow and its individual components.

Language and text-based research data are of particular importance in many disciplines in the humanities. Within the Text+ structure, TGR belongs to their data domain *Collections*, which aims to provide a wide range of language and text-based collections of written, spoken or signed language and texts. Naturally, these collections come in a variety of quality levels regarding the structure of data and metadata. TGR provides highly structured data and metadata in TEI-XML. The *Collections* domain aims to increase the amount of high quality data and therefore encourages and helps researchers to develop fluffy import. This also includes tools to support researchers in the creation, use and provision of FAIR data.

9. Text+ disseminates its service portfolio through the SSH Open Marketplace as entity *tools/services* marked with the keyword *textplus*: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?q=textplus>

10. TGR is a metadata provider for CLARIN: <https://vlo.clarin.eu/search;jsessionid=-F74E31EE0DF2A8AD494A9A9C05E92DD8?0&fq=resourceClass:Text/tg.edition%2Btg.aggregation%2Bxml&fq=dataProvider:TextGrid+Repository&fqType=resourceClass:or&fqType=dataProvider:or>

Within Text+, resources are available for maintaining and further developing TGR. For example, new research tools are connected, corpora are published, workshops are held – and the fluffy workflow is developed. As we explain in section 4, the new publication workflow has been developed by closely following the community’s needs and feedback.

3 TextGrid Repository

TGR is a repository specialised in XML-TEI documents and images of digitised materials, primarily literary texts (Neuroth, Rapp, and Söring 2015). TGR originally started as part of the D-Grid programme and became a pioneering resource for the digital humanities in the German-speaking arena. Research projects can deposit and publish their corpora, collections and editions in TGR free of charge. The repository ensures the long-term preservation¹¹ of the submitted research data and enables access and reuse in various ways. Since 2023, TGR has been continuously certified with CoreTrustSeal (TextGrid 2024).¹²

TGR places a strong emphasis on quality metadata to support the FAIR-ification of the submitted data. In addition to the basic metadata that researchers are required to provide – e.g. author, title and licensing information – it is recommended that documents be tagged with further metadata such as language, genre, author identifiers (through Wikidata or GND, the authority files of the German-speaking arena¹³) and author gender, among other items. These metadata allow for more extensive and faceted literary–historical queries that can contribute to answering specific research questions (Calvo Tello et al. 2023). For example, within a specific project’s data, users can explore whether certain groups of authors tend to write in certain genres or whether they tend to use a particular vocabulary.

Researchers can present their research data in TGR using several project-specific functionalities. The repository facilitates clear attribution to both the data contributor and research project via, for example, a project-specific landing page, persistent identifiers and citation suggestions.¹⁴

TGR is not just a data repository; it also includes a presentation layer for the published texts and images. This feature makes it possible for users to read the texts on screen and work with the data without needing to download them first.

11. TGR may be used as long-term archive as its data is bit-stream preserved by the SUB Göttingen/GWDG. This is evidenced by the (renewed) Core Trust Seal certification of the repository.

12. See: <https://doi.org/10.34894/L1F7BS>

13. See: https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Standardisierung/GND/gnd_node.html

14. TGR provides ePIC handles as PIDs; for more information: https://www.pidconsortium.net/?page_id=74

Users can create their own collections using the “shelf” function (Figure 2).¹⁵ Whether as single texts, specific collections or newly combined corpora, the texts in TGR are available for full-text download in the preferred XML-TEI format, as well as in e-book (EPUB), HTML or plain text formats. The latter makes it easier to input data into many NLP tools, statistical analysis tools like R or topic modelling pipelines. Additionally, descriptive, administrative and technical metadata can be accessed in XML files separately from the full text.

Figure 2: The shelf function of TGR offers the option to compile individual text collections. These can then be downloaded or used in combination with other tools.

Furthermore, the texts are connected to the following third-party tools:

- ▶ **Voyant Tools:** Voyant Tools¹⁶ (Sinclair and Rockwell 2016) offers low-threshold, web-based access to text visualisation and analysis and text collections directly from TGR (via the shelf feature). Voyant allows for output such as word frequency, word distribution and co-occurrence. These elements can provide insights into stylistic features, word clusters, etc., and serve as a starting point for further quantitative research.
- ▶ **Language Resource Switchboard:** Through integration with Switchboard¹⁷ (Zinn 2016), users can process texts in the browser using numerous annotation and analysis tools. This is achieved by accessing exter-

15. <https://textgridrep.org/shelf>

16. Voyant Tools: <https://voyant-tools.org/>

17. Language Resource Switchboard (LRS) or Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>

nal servers so users do not need large computing capacities. When texts are loaded into Switchboard, it automatically recognises the file format and language of the loaded text and suggests tools that work with these features. The analysis then takes place on the website and web server of the selected tool. Switchboard's tool inventory includes services for automatic annotation (constituency parsing, dependency parsing, named entity recognition, etc.) and various distant reading methods such as topic modelling.

- **Annotation Viewer:** Texts can be loaded directly from TGR into Annotation Viewer¹⁸ if the user logs in with the DARIAH authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) (institutional account via eduGAIN or DARIAH account).¹⁹ Free annotation with comments or tags is possible for single words or passages of text. The annotations are saved to the user's account and can be accessed and worked with later. They are stored in a sortable table that can be downloaded for further analysis in spreadsheets (in comma-separated values format). For larger annotation projects, Annotation Viewer's group function can be implemented to facilitate collaborative work.

To date, the majority of projects published in TGR belong to the field of literary studies, and it is especially frequently used by projects in computational literary studies. Their input data stems from digital corpora and digital scholarly editions of literature. Publication in TGR is open to materials in any language and genre, from any research project, and free of charge. When researchers consider TGR for the publication of their data, they can contact the TextGrid team²⁰ for advice and support throughout the entire data publishing process. This communication can happen through direct contact with the developers and those responsible at TGR, or through the DARIAH-DE helpdesk,²¹ which is a joint helpdesk with Text+.

TGR has implemented several controlled vocabularies for metadata. As a common standard, most library catalogues use authority files to identify entities such as authors. Particularly in the humanities fields that work with language- and text-based data, this is frequently needed information for research. Since its beginning, TGR has suggested the use of the authority file system implemented by German-speaking libraries (GND) for the identification of authors (Figure 3). Since 2024, users can use concepts from GND to describe the genre and further themes of the text. Moreover, TGR has integrated the Basic Classification library classification system (Schulz 1991; Calvo Tello, Funk, Kurzawe, Veentjer 2023) for assigning research subjects.²²

18. Annotation Viewer: <https://doc.de.dariah.eu/DARIAH-DE-Annotation-Sandbox/>

19. For more information about the DARIAH AAI see: <https://doc.de.dariah.eu/DARIAH-AAI-Documentation/> .

20. Contact TextGrid: <https://textgrid.de/en/kontakt/>

21. DARIAH-DE helpdesk: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/riBkMh>

22. For details about the role of the GND in Text+, see Kett et al. (2022).

Figure 3: Example entry for “Thomas Mann: Zauberberg”, with author Ida Boy-Ed’s GND identifier highlighted in blue.

4 Data publishing workflow in TGR

Originally, TextGrid was conceived as having several components, such as the TextGrid Laboratory and the TextGrid Repository. In the original conception, researchers would publish their data to TGR using the TextGrid Laboratory (Göbel 2015). The Laboratory was designed to handle single texts and allow researchers to work on them collaboratively, via the various options for editing, annotating and publishing their data collectively.

However, many research teams would prefer to prepare their editions, collections and corpora in environments other than the TextGrid Laboratory and still publish their data in TGR. In a first attempt to address this problem, an import method called Ingest 2 was developed using the TG-import service. For this import method, users were expected to understand the complex metadata model of TGR²³ and create the necessary metadata files that TextGrid requires for publication. In addition, researchers had to use the TG-import part of the Kopal Library of Retrieval and Ingest (koLibRI), a command-line tool based on Java that required skills which the target user group of TGR – researchers in the humanities – were not trained in.

After publishing the CoNSSA (Calvo Tello 2021) and the ELTeC (European Literary Text Collection) corpora (Schöch et al. 2021; Rißler-Pipka et al. 2023), it became clearer to the TextGrid team that a more user-friendly publication

23. For more information about the TGR metadata model see: https://doc.textgrid.de/The-Logical-View_9013285/

workflow was required. The new publication workflow should adhere to the following principles:

1. Users are not expected to understand the entire TextGrid metadata model.
2. Users should utilise technologies they are familiar with (such as XML, xPaths or Jupyter Notebooks).
3. Most of the metadata needed for the publication is expected to be present in the original TEI files.
4. If the metadata is not already available, users should be able to enrich it easily during the publication process.

The workflow handles the creation of the necessary metadata files for publishing in TGR and imports them to the TextGrid storage. After a final check in a closed area, users can publish their data on the productive server of TGR. Each step of the workflow is described in detail in sections 4.1–4.8.

Figure 4: One of the first steps of the import process in the Jupyter Notebook environment.

This publication workflow has been in development since 2023, based on the aforementioned principles. However, the current state described in this article is the result of numerous new features, revisions and other additions. The workflow has been developed through close collaboration with several research teams that have published their project data in TGR in the past years. Three of these projects are presented in section 5. This collaborative exchange took place through personal contact, in-person workshops, introductory sessions and (virtual) meetings. We opted for this methodology instead of analysing the publication workflows of other repositories.

The fluffy publication workflow can be used without prior installation, as it is readily available on the Text+ JupyterHub and the Jupyter4NFDI JupyterHub, as we describe in section 6. It is also possible to run the application on a local machine by using the provided Docker image. To start the application on the Text+ JupyterHub, researchers select the option “Text+ Notebook”. To do the same in

Jupyter4NFDI, a link provided in the README.md of the application repository²⁴ can be used. For many users, Jupyter4NFDI may be the first choice because it is easily accessible even without being affiliated with an academic institution.²⁵

The fluffy import consists of a set of Python command-line tools and a JupyterLab application that aggregates these tools and makes the import functionality available via a user interface. The user interface runs in a notebook (Figure 4), which relies on additional Python, HTML, CSS and JavaScript code. The Jupyter environment provides several options for creating, uploading and downloading files and folders, while also using Jupyter Notebooks for writing text in Markdown, executing code and exploring code output.

In order to use the publication workflow, users need to log in to two different systems: TGR and the Jupyter4NFDI system. As TGR is a DARIAH service, the DARIAH AAI is required, while the Jupyter4NFDI service, which is provided by Helmholtz-associated research centre FZ Jülich, requires the Helmholtz AAI. For both systems, users can use either their institutional account or a free DARIAH account.²⁶

While this paper mainly describes the steps using Jupyter Notebooks, the components are modular. Expert users or projects involving large amounts of data or frequent updates can choose to interact with and upload files to TGR via the command line rather than the Jupyter Notebooks graphical interface. However, this would require knowledge of the tools involved (tg-model, tgclients, tgadmin).

Although this paper focuses primarily on the technical aspects of the publication workflow, the TGR team supports and advises researchers in advance on the metadata quality of their files. We encourage them to send us their TEI files before using the publication workflow to obtain advice about the metadata and suggestions on how to improve its quality. In many cases, these improvements can be made with minimal effort, regardless of whether the researchers ultimately choose to publish the data in TGR.

To showcase the fluffy publication workflow step by step, we use two XML-TEI files from the Folger Digital Texts (a collection of Shakespeare's works)²⁷ as examples.

24. <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/textplus/textplus-io/nb-actions>

25. A non-affiliated researcher may use a DARIAH account, which is available free of charge upon request.

26. For more information about the types of DARIAH user accounts, see <https://doc.de.dariah.eu/DARIAH-User-Administration-Documentation/>.

27. See https://folgerpedia.folger.edu/Folger_Digital_Texts and <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-0fbb2df9-f839-018a-755f-67e9167287b8> for the new project in TGR.

The TEI documents containing the texts to be published in TGR can be uploaded to the Jupyter Cloud via drag-and-drop or by cloning them from a GitHub or GitLab repository. In Figure 5, we have used the drag-and-drop option, which is particularly useful when uploading a small number of files.

Figure 5: Two XML files uploaded in the Jupyter4NFDI environment.

The user can now activate the cell of the main notebook (00-main-app.ipynb), as seen in Figure 6. This notebook offers a variety of options, which we describe in detail in section 6. To use the publication workflow, the user needs to select “Load action group” from the first drop-down menu, followed by “TextGrid import” from the second.

Figure 6: Start of the publication workflow.

When the user clicks the third drop-down menu (“Step”), they can see the eight steps involved in the publication in TGR, each of which we describe in the following subsections.

4.1 Step 1: Select TextGrid servers

At this stage, the user can choose to work on TGR’s test or production server (Figure 7). In both cases, the user can upload their files to a closed environment and make adjustments. The difference between the two servers is that the user can carry out all the steps, including the final publication, on the test server in an environment that can be more easily erased – unlike on the production server. We recommend that users work on the test server first and only move to the production server once they are familiar with the entire process and satisfied with the results. For this publication, we illustrate work on the test server.

Figure 7: Step 1: Users choose the TGR server.

4.2 Step 2: Obtain and store TextGrid session ID

In the second step, the user needs to connect the Jupyter environment with TGR. To do this, they need to provide a TextGrid session ID, which is a long string of characters assigned to a user for a period of time. The graphical interface displays a link (embedded in the text “Get one here if needed” in Figure 8) that leads to the previously mentioned DARIAH AAI. After successful login, the user obtains a session ID, which must be pasted into the form, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Step 2: Connecting the Jupyter environment with the TGR data through the DARIAH AAI.

4.3 Step 3: Select project

In the third step, users choose whether to work on an existing or new TextGrid project. For existing TextGrid projects, users select a project from a list of projects associated with their account. For new users, the existing project list is empty. To create a new project, users need to assign a name to it, as seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Step 3: Selecting an existing project or creating a new project.

4.4 Step 4: Select path to data

At this stage, the user needs to select the location of the data in the Jupyter environment. To do this, they use the folder and file explorer on the left. Once the correct folder containing the TEI files has been selected, the user clicks on “Use selected” and the relevant path is copied into the input field, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Step 4: Selecting the input and output paths.

The output path is selected in a second field. This already contains a default path, but the user can choose a different one.

4.5 Step 5: Select metadata and metadata source

In the previous steps, the user selected only one piece of information at a time, but this fifth step requires considerably more work. In this step, the user has to obtain and edit two YAML files (YAML is a human-readable data serialisation language): “project.yaml” and “collection.yaml.”

“Project.yaml” (Figure 11) is a short file containing several fields, such as the project title, a short description, information on whether the project uses an image as an avatar or a project-specific XSLT stylesheet for transforming TEI into HTML, and the name or names of the collectors. It also contains the URL of an identifier, such as an ORCID ID.

```
{
  "references": [
    "urn:cts:engLit:mds822-32.tpsth1-1599.pdl-eng:1.1"
  ],
  "commentary": "<span>If thou wilt live</span>",
  "fragment": "live with mee",
  "ve_refs": [
    "1.1.t2",
    "1.1.t3",
    "1.1.t4"
  ],
  "idx": "1",
  "urn": "urn:cite2:scaife-viewer:commentary.v1:commentary2",
  "witnesses": [
    {
      "value": "Rs",
      "label": "MS Rodenbach"
    }
  ]
},
```

Figure 11: Step 5: Writing project metadata in the “project.yaml” file.

The other file involved in this step is “collection.yaml” (Figure 12). Each collection within the TextGrid project requires a separate “collection.yaml” file. This file is based on the assumption that most of the metadata required for TGR files can be found in the original XML-TEI files. Thus, the import tool scans all files in the corpus and attempts to find the correct xPaths for information such as author name, language, year of creation and publication, author gender, etc. When the user opens “collection.yaml”, they find suggested xPaths that retrieve information from the TEI files. For example, see Figure 12, which shows suggested xPaths for publication title, URL of the licence and publication date. The user can then modify the proposed xPaths or assign new ones.

```

60 edition:
61   title:
62     value:
63     xpath: //fileDesc//titleStmt//title
64   author:
65     id:
66       value: "gnd:118613723"
67       xpath:
68     fullname:
69       value:
70       xpath:
71     firstname:
72       value: "William"
73       xpath:
74     lastname:
75       value: "Shakespeare"
76       xpath:
77   license:
78     title:
79       value: "CC-NC 3.0"
80     xpath:
81     url:
82       value:
83       xpath: //availability/licence/@target
84   date:
85     value:
86     xpath: //publicationStmt/date
87   place:
88     value:
89     xpath:
90   language:
91     value: "eng"
92     xpath:

```

Figure 12: Step 5: Writing collection metadata in the “collection.yaml” file as constant values or through xPaths.

However, much of the metadata relevant for publication is missing in the original TEI files. For example, a project that edits novels by French women authors will probably not have collected metadata about the authors' gender, language or nationality. The researcher working on this project might consider this information obvious because it applies to all texts in the corpus. Although the researcher could modify all the individual TEI files, in our experience, they are reluctant to do so once the project is closed or the funding has ended. Instead, the publication workflow gives them the opportunity to simply add this metadata as fixed and global values for all files within a collection, which is then stored in TGR and displayed as facets. This is done through the subfield “value,” which can be seen in Figure 12 with the subfields of “author ID”, “first name” and “last name”, “licence” and “language”. Assigning metadata through fixed values for the entire collection is a very simple way for projects to have quality metadata applied to all of the project’s documents (potentially thousands of files) in one single step. This is one of the aspects that makes the workflow more fluffy and one of the principles of the workflow.

4.6 Step 6: Upload to TextGrid

In this step, the user can make final adjustments to the project files before uploading them to TGR (Figure 13). Using the metadata assigned in step 5, the workflow creates a project-specific file that controls the different options

of the TextGrid project. This file is called “portalconfig.xml.” Here, the user can, for example, manage which facets they want applied to the portal. The user can also edit a “readme.md” file, which will be displayed on the project’s landing page. These adjustments are not required, however, and the user can skip them and upload their files to TGR.

Figure 13: Step 6: Editing final files and uploading them to TGR.

The user can choose to upload either the collection files (TEI and metadata files), the other files (XSLT, avatar, portal config, etc.) or both at once to their new TextGrid project. TextGrid projects have a stable URL, which works as an identifier.²⁸

After a successful upload, the researcher can view the metadata and files in a closed beta area of TGR, which is only accessible to project members. Access is possible after logging in to TGR via DARIAH AAI, as explained above. After reviewing the files in the beta area, the researcher can decide to return to any of the previous steps to modify and improve the metadata and update the files.

4.7 Step 7: Check publication

Once the user is satisfied with the rendering of the metadata and the HTML conversion in the closed area of the portal, they need to run a final test before publishing the data (Figure 14). Several tests are then run on the required fields and the validity of their values. The output of this step is a log file containing the results, showing all warnings and errors.

28. For example: <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-0fbb2df9-f839-018a-755f-67e9167287b8>.

Figure 14: Step 7: Check publication.

4.8 Step 8: Publish

If step 7 is successful, the user can publish their data. For publication to take place, the user is required to confirm their decision to publish and signal their understanding that this step cannot be undone (at least not on the production server) by writing the word “yes” (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Step 8: Publish.

After this step, the workflow produces a log file containing the results of the process. The data is now visible in TGR (on the test or production servers) to anyone, without needing to log in.

5 New published projects in TextGrid Repository

As examples, we briefly present three collections from projects published in 2024, which were the first to use this new workflow: a collection of corpora in Romance languages, a collection of French novels, and a project on folklore from the Caucasus. As mentioned in section 4, we engaged in continuous practical and personal interaction with the researchers that wished to publish their data in TGR.

5.1 CLiGS Textbox

The first project is the CLiGS Textbox, which encompasses nine literary corpora in French, Italian, Spanish and Portuguese encoded in TEI. These corpora were originally collected for the CLiGS project by Christof Schöch, Ulrike Henny-Krahmer and José Calvo Tello. The literary texts include short stories, novellas, novels and drama (plays).²⁹

Figure 16: Landing page for the CLiGS Textbox project on the TGR portal.

The corpora had been already published on Zenodo³⁰ and GitHub,³¹ two platforms which present both advantages and disadvantages. One disadvantage is the fact that TEI files are not converted into HTML, making it difficult to read the texts. In the context of the call for user stories for the German NFDI consortium Text+ (Rißler-Pipka et al. 2021), a user story³² focused on this project (Henny-Krahmer et al. 2023). That motivated us to take this corpus as a test case for the development of the workflow tool. This project is interesting in several regards, particularly because a person involved in the original composition of the corpus is now part of the TextGrid team. Moreover, the project includes several medium- to small-sized corpora, collected by different researchers and with a certain degree of heterogeneity in their metadata.

29. For a more detailed description, the CLiGS Textbox [project's landing page](#), the list of files in TGR, and Schöch et al. (2019) can be consulted.

30. Christof Schöch, Ulrike, José Calvo, & Katrin B. (2018). cligs/textbox: Almost Summer Release (v.4.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1254483>

31. Github repository for CLiGs: <https://github.com/cligs/textbox>

32. The referenced user story: <https://text-plus.org/themen-dokumentation/user-storys-2020/user-story-330/>

For this project (Figure 16), several of the features used, including the project-specific facets, the landing page, and the use of Basic Classification for description, were originally implemented in TGR for ELTeC³³ as part of the Text+ work programme. In addition, this project is the first to include genre annotation using the concepts from the German authority files GND. The TextGrid metadata files contain the identifiers of these GND entities, thereby linking them to the original authority files via URIs.

5.2 Eighteenth-Century French Novels 1751-1800

Another corpus published using the new workflow is a collection of eighteenth-century French novels 1751–1800 (Figure 17).³⁴ The corpus was collected by Julia Röttgermann as part of the Mining and Modeling Text project, led by Christof Schöch at the University of Trier.

Figure 17: Landing page of the Collection of Eighteenth-Century French Novels 1751–1800 project on the TGR portal.

A detailed description of the corpus can be found in Röttgermann (2024). Similar to other projects in TGR, some of the metadata are displayed in the portal as facets in the left-hand menu. These facets provide a user-friendly overview of the project that is not available on other platforms like GitHub³⁵ or Zenodo³⁶.

33. ELTeC in TGR: <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-99d098e9-b60f-98fd-cda3-6448e07e619d>. See also Reißler-Pipka et al. (2023).
34. The landing page for the Collection Eighteenth-Century French Novels 1751-1800 project in TGR: <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-c594f9cf-08fd-6086-8379-66c84a31c11a>
35. Github repository for the Collection Eighteenth-Century French Novels 1751-1800 project: <https://github.com/MiMoText/roman18>
36. Zenodo publication of the Collection Eighteenth-Century French Novels 1751-1800 project: <https://zenodo.org/records/10404966>

For example, 159 novels in this corpus are assigned to male authors, 35 to female authors, and in six cases the gender of the author is unknown. This corpus uses one of the facets developed for the ELTeC project, namely text length. This metadata shows that 60% of the novels are classified as short, about a quarter as medium length and only 36 novels as long. Of the 121 different authors present in the collection, the ones with the largest number of texts are François-Thomas-Marie de Baculard d'Arnaud (14 texts), Voltaire (nine), Denis Diderot, Isabelle de Charrière and Marie-Jeanne Riccoboni (six texts each).

5.3 Caucasian Folklore

Another third project that recently published its research data as TEI documents in TGR is the Caucasian Folklore project (Figure 18).³⁷ The research data includes folkloristic texts in several languages from different Caucasian language families and in various scripts (Figure 19). These texts serve as primary data for comparative narrative research and are captured with appropriate markup during the research process. One of the project's requirements was to make the metadata and annotations accessible, in addition to the texts. This is achieved by offering both access to the original XML files and in-browser viewing of the data. For this purpose, a special XSL transformation was applied, allowing various metadata from the TEI files to be presented in the HTML transformation. Currently, this includes annotations on the texts' type and motif structure.

The screenshot shows the TextGrid Repository interface. At the top left is the TextGrid logo. To its right is a search bar with the placeholder text 'Suchbegriff' and a magnifying glass icon. Below the search bar is the text 'Erweiterte Suche'. To the right of the search bar are two dropdown menus: 'Inhalte' and 'Dokumentation'. In the top right corner, there is a 'Regal' icon with '0' items and a language selector set to 'English'. The main content area is titled 'Kaukasische Folklore'. Below the title is a paragraph of text: 'Das Ziel des vorliegenden Projekts ist es, folkloristische Texte aus den mündlichen Repertoires der im Kaukasus zahlreich vertretenen Ethnien und Sprachen zu sammeln und sie gemäß den Anforderungen der FAIR-Datenprinzipien zugänglich zu machen. [mehr...]'. To the right of this text is a grid of colored squares, each containing a language code (e.g., tab, abk, lzz, agx, tin, kbd, tly, ukr, ava, hye, azj, aqc, huz, nog, kva, khv, akv, bdk, bbl, oss, xmf, xdq, kat, qar, udi, bph, gdo, mh, gn, ani, cji, rus, grc, ady, jdt, krc, kot, ttt, tkr, kji, kry, kap, ugh, kum, abq, sva, rut, odo, tpe, tez, uby, che, jbe). Below the grid is a button labeled 'Anzeige anpassen'. At the bottom of the page, there is a link 'Awarische Folklore' and a button '+ Zum Regal hinzufügen'.

Figure 18: Landing page of the Caucasian Folklore project on the TGR portal.

37. The landing page for the Caucasian Folklore project in TGR: <https://textgridrep.org/project/TGPR-e8f00d53-6ae6-9d31-c530-66cec1a28e16>

Figure 19: Display of filters and non-Latin scripts in the Caucasian Folklore project.

6 Notebook Actions

Having provided detailed insights into the research data itself, we return to the underlying infrastructure, specifically the use of Jupyter Notebooks, JupyterHub and Notebook Actions.³⁸

Figure 20: The fluffy workflow is preinstalled in the Docker image labelled “Text+ Notebook”.

Implementing a workflow as a Jupyter Notebook and making it available on the Text+ JupyterHub (Figure 20) are important steps in establishing an infrastructure that is easily accessible to the community and provides not only

38. <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/textplus/textplus-io/nb-actions>

tools but also appropriate computing resources. Jupyter Notebooks has been heavily used by several research areas for different purposes, including by researchers in the humanities (Dombrowski et al. 2019, Gomes et al. 2024). Significant improvements are currently under development, both in terms of software and infrastructure.

The successful implementation of the fluffy workflow has demonstrated the viability of this approach. Originally developed as a single-purpose application, it has since been extended into a flexible, notebook-based framework that supports the creation and execution of custom actions and workflows. Now called “Notebook Actions”, the application has evolved into a generic, multipurpose tool, where actions can be implemented as Python functions or by wrapping existing command-line tools, which are then made accessible through a forms-based user interface.

The application enables the seamless combination of automatic and manual steps, as required in complex workflows, by leveraging the capabilities of the Jupyter technology. This makes it particularly well suited for interactive work with data and tools. The application already includes a number of useful actions (Figure 21), making it usable without expert knowledge. Users can also define their own functions and commands, integrating them into the interface as reusable actions or workflow steps. Built-in editing features allow for the creation, customisation and removal of actions and workflows directly within the user interface.

Figure 21: Multiple useful actions are available in Notebook Actions, which builds upon the fluffy workflow application.

Figure 22: The dialogue for the action “OCR with Tesseract: text” makes the OCR command-line tool Tesseract available, executing the `tesseract` command behind the scenes with the parameters provided by the user: input/output folder and language. The output format is text, and other actions are available for generating PDF and ALTO. Action dialogues such as this one are created and edited in the UI.

We plan to increase the number of available actions (Figure 22) and thus cover an ever-growing number of use cases, while using infrastructure already in place and not requiring additional services. Additionally, using Jupyter Notebooks benefits from the ongoing development of the Jupyter4NFDI service, which offers an increasing number of useful features, such as persistent storage, the possibility to run Docker images accessible via URLs, and `repo2docker` functionality, which allow code within a repository to be run in a Jupyter environment, provided the repository adheres to certain conventions.

7 Conclusion

In this article, we have introduced the new fluffy publication workflow in TGR, lowering the barriers to publishing research data in the form of collections of XML-TEI files. We acknowledge that researchers create data in very different environments. The new publication process aims to integrate resources more easily and with metadata of higher quality.

The support provided by the various project partners and the possibility to add metadata through fixed values and xPaths in a familiar environment such as Jupyter Notebooks make the process smoother and much more user-friendly, while at the same time improving and validating the metadata and thus its compliance with the FAIR principles. For future steps and new developments,

we want to consider more projects and therefore more diversity in the input data. We are aware that the fluffy import cannot yet support the publication of many different types of files and use cases. An important next step is to consider projects that also include images and digitisation files of various kinds.

One technical as well as social barrier to the publication of textual research data is related to formats. While TGR specialises in XML-TEI files, many researchers and projects cannot meet this criterion because their data is in plain text or even Word files. The latter is in general not fit for archiving research data due to its proprietary format restrictions. Therefore, it is rarely supported by research data infrastructures. We claim that, in the medium term, it is important to also offer solutions to research projects that do not come from digital humanities backgrounds and need help converting and enriching their textual data into highly structured and FAIR data using XML-TEI.

Finally, we would like to express our conviction that libraries, computing centres and other infrastructure providers should play a more active and supportive role in the enrichment and publication of research data. TGR was conceived and continues to operate as a self-service platform where anyone can publish research data without our assistance. We are working to improve this with the more user-friendly fluffy import, while the team also offers more active support, moving clearly towards a shared responsibility.

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